

Sensor deployment to support the integrated energy management system in residential buildings in ReCO2ST

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Abstract

The EU ReCO2ST project improves the energy efficiency and comfort levels of older structures by refurbishing them. These buildings are spread across Europe to account for the variability of climate that can be experienced on the continent. [1]–[3] The project needs Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) to provide sensory information to an Intelligent Energy Management System (IEMS) to improve functionality of older buildings that have poor energy efficiency.

WSNs are becoming a major focus point in how we can provide more information in support of the Internet of Things [4], [5], [3]. As these WSNs become more prevalent there is more reason to focus on how to configure and deploy them systematically and robustly. This paper looks at using Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) sensors to provide this systematic and robust setup. A WSN's system quality and robustness are dependent on factors such as the communication protocols, (how data is sent), how data is stored and how its data is accessed. Using COTS sensors, a WSN can be created with a standard base technology, and this allows for easy integration of many types of sensors.

Keywords: wireless sensor network, energy management, refurbishment, energy efficiency, retrofit

1. Introduction

The ReCO2ST project (<https://reco2st.eu/>) aims to bring older buildings up to similar standards of energy efficiency that we see in modern or newly built structures [1], [2], [7], [8]. The project helps them to become more energy efficient with three systematic approaches: A refurbishment assessment tool, which helps building owners make relevant decisions, plans for renovation through Integrated Project Delivery and finally a retrofit refurbishment kit or retrofit-kit for targeted renovation.

The retrofit-kit includes many cost efficient and modular technologies that make them ideal for refurbishment of a building. These technologies are: Vacuum Insulation Panels (VIP), Modular Photovoltaics, Smart Windows with heating and cooling capacity, Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), Intelligent Energy Management (IEMS), Nature Based Technologies (NBT) and Cool Materials and Solutions [2], [3], [7], [9]. This paper focuses on the Wireless Sensor aspect of the retrofit kit and its relation to the IEMS as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: High Level IEMS Feedback Loop

The retrofit-kit is essentially a network of sensors that has been developed to provide information to a centralized cloud system. The information collected in this cloud system is used by the Intelligent Energy Management System (IEMS) to manage the energy consumption of the building. The IEMS will control heating, hot water and air conditioning using an algorithm that takes in both user comfort levels from tenants in the building (via survey) and via sensor information.

The role of the WSN is to measure environmental parameters in the building to enable the IEMS to make intelligent decisions in controlling the ReCO2ST technologies to optimise comfort levels and energy efficiency.

The key aspect of the IEMS is the intelligent control of the Building Energy Management (BEM) system [4], [6], [10], [11]. Figure 2 demonstrates how the sensor network (within the dotted lines) feeds information to the IEMS. The IEMS algorithmically utilizes this information and makes decisions on where to apply the different technologies it controls (Domestic Hot Water-DHW, Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning-HVAC, and Evaporative Cooling-CAVE). By providing additional sensed data to the IEMS, it has more and better information to make decisions [10].

Figure 2: IEMS Overview

The ICT monitoring system has been developed using largely Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) components integrated to give a sensing system that can be retrofitted into buildings for a number of usages in the project. These are listed below

1. To monitor and measure the effects of the ReCO2ST technologies integrated into the Demo buildings
2. To provide additional information and granularity for operation of an IEMS being deployed in Cadiz Demo site

To enable users to view the data the sensing system needs to store the results on a cloud-based platform. This influenced the choice of sensors used. Tyndall developed a wireless interface through LoRa [12] and made the data recorded available via a cloud service. For the remaining sensors, an off the shelf solution from Monnit was used. These are low cost robust accurate sensors that come with a standard cloud storage system that can be viewed via a built in GUI or REST API via web services.

2. Sensor Requirements

The ReCO2ST sites were located in Cadiz (Spain), Vevey (Switzerland), Frederikshavn (Denmark), and Brunel (United Kingdom). The retrofit requirements of technologies were unique at each of the 4 demo sites, therefore bespoke sensing needs were identified as shown in Table 1.

To ensure consistency in measured data a sensor retrofit kit was developed that contained a suite of sensors.

From these requirements two principal systems were developed and integrated, Monnit and LoRa.

Description	Cadiz	Vevey	Frederikshavn	Brunel
K Type Thermocouple (Thermowell)				
K Type Thermocouple				
CO2				
Particulate Matter				
VOC				
Ambient Air Temp				
Humidity/Temperature				
Electrical Energy Meters				

Table 1: Sensor requirements of each site involved in the ReCO2ST project

The sensor requirements are defined by two parameters:

1. What information is needed to control the IEMS (primary reason).
2. What information is needed to monitor the energy technologies that are put in place (Cloud storage for partners in ReCO2ST).

For example, in Cadiz, the air quality sensors provided have two uses, one is to provide information on the monitored apartments and therefore give useful information to the IEMS and the second is to measure the performance of the nature based technology that is deployed in the staircases.

2.1 Monitoring the ReCO2ST Technologies

The technologies used throughout the project excluding Wireless Sensor Networks and IEMS are: Vacuum Insulation Panels (VIP) which provide insulation, Modular Photovoltaics to store and use sustainable energies, Smart Windows with heating and cooling capacity, Nature Based Technologies (NBT) that contribute to air quality and Cool Materials and Solutions that provide cooling via reflective paints.

Technology	Affected Variable	Sensor Type
VIP	Indoor Ambient Temperature	Indoor Ambient Temperature Sensors, K-type Thermocouples
Modular Photovoltaics	Energy Supplied	Energy Meters
Smart Windows	Indoor Ambient Temperature	Indoor Ambient Temperature Sensors
NBT	Air Quality	CO ₂ , VOC, and Particulate Matter Sensors
Cool Materials	Indoor Ambient Temperature	K-type Thermocouples

Table 2: Technology vs Affected Variables vs Applied Sensor Type

Table 2 displays the various technologies installed, the variables that they each affect, and the type of sensor used to monitor the effect of this technology.

2.2 Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) Sensor Systems

One of the principal considerations when selecting sensing platforms for ReCO₂ST was that standardised COTS components should be used to enable cost effective, re-configurable and scalable sensing capability. Parts from Monnit were selected for all the basic environmental parameters, as this gave a fast, cost-effective deployment with excellent support and remote access to data storage. The use of a low power system such as Monnit provides the opportunity in the future to eliminate battery replacement through the addition of energy harvesting. In addition to this, a LoRa based solution was developed to enable interfacing of sensors with a third-party cloud service. This gave the flexibility to add specialised sensors more easily into the system as needed.

One example of where we integrated sensors into this standard LoRa solution was the air quality sensors from NanoSense. Monnit did not support the air quality parameters required for the project (CO₂ levels, VOC levels, Particulate Matter). Nanosense was chosen because project partner UTRC had completed a number of independent assessments to validate their accuracy of the sensor. At the time of development, Nanosense only supported wired interfaces or an EnOcean wireless interface, so Tyndall developed a LoRa interface compatible with MODBUS TCP to enable integration into standard IEMS control bus.

3. Sensor Network

Using standard interfaces, it is possible to integrate a large number of sensors from different vendors, or to design and integrate bespoke sensors. It also enables easy integration into standardised building control systems such as MODBUS TCP that is used by the IEMS. Figure 3 below shows the interface stack that is used on ReCO₂ST for the Wireless Sensing Systems. This underlying complexity is abstracted from the user who interacts with the data via standard web-based interfaces.

Figure 3: Standards based technology stack

The advantage of using the system chosen is self-evident. The user can access data while being abstracted from all the different layers of technology. The researchers are able to retrieve data through simple user interfaces.

Figure 4 below shows the implementation in Cadiz. The ReCO2ST project uses three communication protocols to route information through the buildings to the gateways. These protocols are LoRaMAC, 868MHz Radio Frequency and MODBUS Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). The gateways are then used to pass information to the cloud service.

LoRaMac or LoRa is the physical layer of communications in LoRaWAN. By using the physical layer only, it is possible to send information to our gateway and then use our own storage methods. The 868MHz radio frequency communication protocol is used by Monnit sensors and is developed by Monnit. The MODBUS TCP system is used by the IEMS team in Cadiz to pull data from the sensors. Because of this a gateway that stores information and allows access to this data via MODBUS TCP was developed by Tyndall.

Figure 4 also reveals some of the underlying detail of the deployment in Cadiz, where a number of different radio and wired interfaces are used to enable seamless communication with different type of sensors to the user. The user is unaware of this complexity as they only access data through standard interfaces.

The air quality sensors from Nanosense use MODBUS wired interfaces. Tyndall has integrated some off the shelf LoRa radio modules to enable wireless transmission back to a gateway via a modem. The Monnit sensors using a proprietary 868MHz air interface are also routed back to the same Ethernet modem via a MODBUS TCP gateway. At this point both systems are now communicating with standard internet TCP/IP protocols. The IEMS can either access data via MODBUS TCP or TCP/IP interfaces.

Data is then stored in a cloud system. In this case the Monnit sensors and Nanosense sensors are on different cloud systems, but the user uses standard REST API commands for both systems.

Figure 4: Cadiz Data Flow from Sensor to end user

The network in Cadiz is comprised of Monnit COTS sensors and other sensors that were not available commercially from Monnit. The other sensors have now been configured to provide information in a similar way to those from Monnit using LoRa. The Monnit sensors and Tyndall configured LoRa based sensors all connect to the same MODBUS TCP master. An example of these other sensors are the Nanosense air quality sensors previously mentioned.

4. LoRa System Development

4.1 LoRa Radio to LoRa Gateway Development

LoRa is a long-range low power wide area network (LPWAN). It is used for the transfer of small amounts of data over long distances at low power [12] [13]. This makes it suitable for many IoT solutions. The LoRa radio protocol facilitates development of a secure and private network which in this case is preferable to other protocols such as Sigfox or LTE which require the use provided networks that charge a fee for access.[14] Using a bespoke LoRa network also guarantees coverage whereas Sigfox and LTE are reliant on the services provided.

This system uses the following COTS components.

1. Pycom Lopy 4 LoRa Radio Module for the sensor and gateway (Standard UART, SPI and I2C interfaces)
2. Raspberry Pi microcomputer for the gateway controller

4.2 LoRa Radio to MODBUS TCP Gateway Development

MODBUS is a communication protocol that allows for a master device to request information from a slave device. In MODBUS, the master uses internet protocol.

For the Cadiz demonstration site, the gateway used is configured in such a way that the Gateway allows access to the most recent information via a MODBUS TCP request. The Raspberry Pi takes in the information from the Lopy4 via LoRa then stores the information in a particular register or storage address. It is stored in such a way that when the master makes a request it can specify from where it wants to get that data.

5. Sensor Deployment Tools and Verification

A key challenge in creating reliable sensor networks is ensuring robust communications between the gateway and the sensors. The sensor kit needs to be deployed so that the Gateways are always within reach of the sensor's wireless communication range. To ensure this, tests need to be undertaken to show that the Monnit and LoRa sensors are capable of reaching their relative gateways on-site.

To model and simulate the exact systems that the network being deployed is extremely difficult to do accurately and is time consuming. To mitigate this, Tyndall developed a radio survey device that can test the signals emitted by the sensor devices.

5.1 Radio Survey Device

Radio communication performance can vary given certain circumstances. The received signal strength depends on obstacles between the transmitter and receiver, composition of such obstacles, the different paths that the radio signals take and how they constructively or de-constructively interact, the transmission power of the transmitter and many other factors. Most buildings are not similar enough to use radio tests from one building to infer how it will perform in another. A radio survey device was created in Tyndall to perform quick, on site tests, to determine where to position the transmitters and receiver to optimise the chance that communication would be successful.

Figure 5: Radio Survey Device

The radio survey device is a simple setup of a LoRa transmitter (sensor) and a LoRa receiver (gateway) as shown in Figure 5 above. The transmitter sends a simple string repeatedly at a regular interval. The receiver knows what string it is supposed to receive and compares what it receives to what was expected. The receiver also stores the transmitter power (P-TX) that was used to send the message, the Received Signal Strength Index (RSSI), the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) and the Message Error Rate (MER- percentage of messages not received). The LoRa protocol uses a chirp spread spectrum that uses wideband chirps (frequency sweeps) to encode information. The Spreading Factor is the length of time over which the frequency sweep occurs. Increasing this will improve the likelihood of a successful transmission but will increase the time on air and therefore increase power. The coding rate refers to the proportion of transmitted bits that actually carry data i.e. if the coding rate is 4/8, we are transmitting twice as many bits as have useful information. It is a method of adding parity bits so errors can be recovered at the receiving end [15],

The RSSI and SNR are measures of the signal strength and the higher these numbers are the better the margin and greater confidence that it is a robust link. However, this does not indicate if the data has arrived and its error content. The MER is a measure of how often, good, readable transmissions are getting through. Using a combination of these factors as shown in Table 3 and Table 4 it is possible to determine whether the sensor is appropriately setup in that position. The controllable variables are the time on air, the transmission power, and the spreading factor. These can be changed if the RSSI and SNR are low in a given configuration. By increasing the Transmission Power and Spreading Factor the likelihood of successful transmissions and a better MER are increased.

Timestamp	RSSI	SNR	Time On Air	P-TX	Spreading Factor	Coding Rate	MER	Messages No
1591864087	-120	4	14	2	7	4_5	0	1
1591864097	-119	5	14	2	7	4_5	.33	3
1591864117	-121	5	14	2	7	4_5	.5	6

Table 3: Radio Survey Output Example Unsuccessful Transmission

Timestamp	RSSI	SNR	Time On Air	P-TX	Spreading Factor	Coding Rate	MER	Messages No
1591864087	-96	6	14	2	7	4_5	0	1
1591864097	-91	5	14	2	7	4_5	0	2
1591864107	-97	6	14	2	7	4_5	0	3

Table 4: Radio Survey Output Example: Successful Transmission

Table 3 shows an example of Tyndall's radio survey device output format with 3 failed and 3 successful messages (this equates to a MER of 0.5 or a message failure rate of 50%). Table 4 shows a separate example of Tyndall's radio survey device output format with 3 successful messages of 3 sent. In this example, Table 3 shows what to expect if the transmitter and gateway are not in an ideal position whereas Table 4 exemplifies a situation where they are placed close enough together.

5.2 LoRa Capability Testing

In the Cadiz demo site, there is a challenge whereby the sensor needs to be placed inside a concrete duct with 20cm of concrete between the sensor and the gateway. It was not possible to go on site to test the signal quality through this concrete so a simple test was completed to give confidence that the sensing system could communicate in these conditions

The tests conducted determined whether the LoRa radio selected could successfully transmit through concrete to another radio at different transmission powers and spreading factors.

Figure 6: LoRa Capability Testing Setup

To test this the receiver and sensor were placed at either side of a residential building and switched on, as shown in Figure 6. The transmitter sent a predefined message to the receiver at regular intervals. When the message was received the receiver checked the message to determine whether it was the predefined message as expected or if there was an error in the message. The transmitter signal was travelling through 3 concrete walls estimated to be of 20cm thickness.

Signal reflection and the medium materials of objects within the residential building distorts the results of these tests. These tests were understood not to be a way of quantifying the signal attenuation but instead as a method of determining a high level of confidence on how the radio would function in a similar situation. Using a high margin of success-as shown by the 0% error rate in Table 5 below, can give a level of confidence as opposed to a definitive measurement of signal attenuation.

Although these testing methodologies were indicative but not exact or perfect, to test in a manner that was qualitative would have been both costly and beyond the scope of the project.

The radio in this setup was capable of transmitting at 2dB (its lowest Transmission Power setting) without dropping any messages. It was also tested in its highest possible Transmission Power setting. Table 5 shows the results of each setting. Spreading Factor was consistently applied at its lowest setting of 7 (shortest transmission time).

Transmission Power	Spreading Factor	RSSI (Signal Strength) Average	SNR (Signal to Noise Ratio) Average	MER (Message Error Rate)
2dB (Minimum)	7	-117.75dB	2.75	0%
14dB (Maximum)	7	-109dB	6.54	0%

Table 5: LoRa Capability Testing Results

From experimentation with the device, it was found that the radio can function at near 0% MER up to approximately -120dB and as low as -1 SNR. Even though the RSSI and SNR are significantly worse with the lower transmission power, the radio did not drop any messages. This gives us a high level of confidence in the radio's capabilities for the needs of the project.

5.3 Future Work

One issue is that the proposed radio systems all need to be powered by a fixed power outlet. This is a problem since some temperature sensors will be needed in places where there is not any access to the mains. To combat this an embedded temperature sensor will be developed that is battery operated and uses a LoRa radio to communicate with Tyndall developed gateway. Tyndall is also working on technologies such as micro-power management and energy harvesting to minimise power consumption, maximise the use of ambient energies where available and prolong battery life [16], [17].

Figure 7: Potential low power setup temperature sensor with LoRa radio technology

The aim of this sensor is to take the ambient temperature every 30 minutes and transmit the data and go into a deep low power sleep. The embedded system will be powered by a 3000mAh coin cell battery and will aim to have a lifespan of greater than 5 years.

6. Conclusions

The setup and deployment of the sensor systems in this project required multiple complicated networks and making the information readily available for both the IEMS and users analysing the impact of technologies applied to the refurbished buildings. The COTS sensors provide an easily scalable system that is well supported. The LoRa capable sensors configured by Tyndall will allow for the addition of other sensors outside of Monnit to the system.

The blending of the COTS network with the developed LoRa-radio based sensor network show how this system can be developed to create a system that can seamlessly handle multiple types of sensors and protocols. The challenge provided is to create a wireless network that is robust and ensures that data will always be available for the IEMS to utilize and work continues to improve the reliability of the communications infrastructure and battery life of the wireless sensors used for future retrofit systems.

The system adds value to the ReCO2ST project by ensuring granularity and consistent delivery of data. It also allows for wireless sensors to be retrofit along with a given combination ReCO2ST enabling technologies to form the toolkit. This toolkit, in turn, helps improve the energy efficiency of the building without compromising the comfort of tenants.

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